

Career Development Domains as Correlates of Career Readiness and Selection among Grade 10 Students: Input to Career Information Activities

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ABSTRACT: Students are unsure as to whether they are prepared and competent to choose a class that will make the best use of their strengths and skills at this time. That is why this study aims to determine the Career Development Domains correlates to Career Readiness and Career Selection and how it can be used to career information activities. The researcher used a researcher-made survey instrument that was divided into three parts. The design used in this study is descriptive-correlational research methodology led to the achievement of the goals of the study, which was conducted with the participation of one hundred thirty students in the tenth grade during the academic year 2022-2023 in San Antonio National High School, San Antonio, Quezon. The findings demonstrated that all the indicators stated in Career Development Domain such as interests, skills, problem-solving, and opportunities shows a high level of awareness. Secondly, it also shows that indicators of Career Readiness such as self-efficacy, teamwork, decision-making, organization, effective communication, and goal setting shows a very high level of awareness. Thirdly, it is found that indicators in Career Selection such as talents, abilities, academic achievement, and parents' advice were highly manifested. And lastly, the result shows that there is a significant relationship between the Career Development Domain and both Career Readiness and Career Selection.

KEYWORDS: Career Development Domain, Career Readiness, Career Selection

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Monika (2018), selecting a path to go with one's professional life is a difficult and involved procedure. Even if some people have no trouble making decisions, others struggle when it comes to choosing a path for their professional life. As a result, one of the most important steps in meeting students' needs in terms of career planning was figuring out the challenges they face when making decisions about their future careers.

Afanasiev et al. (2018) said that the problem of enhancing the level of vocational instruction provided by higher education institutions was brought to light as a direct result of the imperative to achieve educational parity with other countries' systems. Studies have shown that the effectiveness of early career guidance work with students who will eventually attend universities is closely related to the solution to this problem. When viewed in this light, career counseling emerges as one of the most crucial and time-sensitive responsibilities of today's schools.

Buraga and Caballero (2018) said that one of the components of the guidance program at the institution where the students are enrolled, the career and placement unit, is one of the services that helps the students get ready for the careers of the future. Students are assisted by the career counselors in determining their interests in the working world and in showcasing their talents and capabilities via the implementation of various career services.

Abubakar (2018) said that students receive assistance during their time in school as part of a guidance service with the goal of improving the overall quality of each student's potential.

In accordance with this, the Department of Education published the Memorandum DM-OUCI-2021-0015. According to this document, the objective of the Career Guidance program is to provide students with assistance in assessing their options and making decisions that are relevant to their career pathing. These activities include making plans, selecting their educational plan exits (higher education, employment, entrepreneurship, and middle level skills development), and getting ready for their chosen track and strand for their senior year of high school.

According to Fernandes and Bance (2015), a person is said to be suffering from career indecision when they are unable to decide on a certain path of action even though they recognize the need of making a commitment. Indecisiveness about a future vocation can be defined as a failure to choose an occupation to pursue.

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Keeping this in mind, the researcher has an interest in learning more about how the career guidance program can help to improve the level of preparedness and selection made by students in grade 10 when it comes to choosing their career. As an Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teacher and an aspirant Guidance Counselor, the researcher sees the need of the students to assess how the career development domains can help to address their issues as a student and be able to select and be ready in choosing the career they want to pursue in the future. In times that the researcher will asks some of her students, most of the students doesn't know yet or still confused to what they really want to pursue which leads to the interest in knowing the variables what they should consider in selecting their career and how would they know if they are ready in choosing a career. Because of this, the researcher plans to concentrate researching on the career development domains and how it can help the students to select and be ready in choosing a career that may be used in the future. This research may assist students in becoming job-ready and deciding which vocations to pursue.

The researcher knows that conducting the study properly may greatly help the students to be ready in selecting the career path that they will choose one day. This may help in the country to lessen the number of unemployed and underemployed graduates as well. The researcher also believes that the outcomes of the study was a great aid to students in enhancing their ability to select their career path and be ready for the career that they have chosen. The Guidance Counselor or the Designated Teacher are the one responsible in the implementation of the improvements and making use of the career development domain to become more prepared and capable of choosing a career.

II. METHOD

In this study, descriptive-correlational design was utilized. According to Curtis et al. (2015), correlational research can be utilized to assess prevalence and correlations across variables, as well as to foresee occurrences using data and knowledge that is currently available. McCombes (2022), said that the design aims at accomplishing the following goals: as well as to double-check the existing connections and derive broad conclusions from the specific one's relationships. These objectives are intended to be met through the design.

The respondents of the study were the 130 Grade 10 students at San Antonio National High School (SANHS), San Antonio, Quezon. The researcher chooses SANHS as the school to conduct her study because the researcher works there, and it is easier to have access in gathering data of the respondents.

The researcher used a simple random sampling technique in choosing the number of respondents. The researcher used 130 samples from 298 Grade 10 students. There are seven sections in Grade 10 that have 149 males and 149 females with a total of 298 students. The researcher randomly selected a maximum of 19 students per section.

The researcher chose them as respondents because she believes that students in this grade level should know what career path they wanted to pursue before leaving or graduating from junior high school. She also believes that these students have a brighter future if they already know what career they want when they finish their schooling.

. In this study, the researcher used a self-made questionnaire validated through the validation of the experts in the field of Guidance and Counseling. The questionnaire was divided into three parts using 1 - 4 Likert Scale. 1 which No level of awareness, 2 as low level of awareness, 3 as moderate level of awareness, and 4 as high level of awareness. Part 1 of the questionnaire is Career Development Domains in terms of interest, skills, problem solving, and opportunities. Part 2 of the questionnaire is Career Readiness in terms of self-efficacy, teamwork, decision making, organization, effective communication, and goal setting. It uses 1 - 4 Likert Scale as 1 very low level of readiness, 2 low level of readiness, 3 high level of readiness, and 4 very high level of readiness. Part 3 of the questionnaire is a Career Selection in terms of talents, abilities, academic achievement, and parents' advice using a 1 - 4 Likert Scale as 1 not manifested, 2 somewhat manifested, 3 moderately manifested, 4 highly manifested. It focuses and measures the knowledge of the students in each variable specifically knowing if the students are ready in selecting their career path. The goal of the tool was to know how the career development domains, career readiness, and selections helped the students in selecting and be ready in choosing their career path.

The researcher made a self-survey questionnaire then validated by the experts in Guidance and Counseling. After the validation, a permission letter to the principal was made to conduct the pilot testing of the study and to facilitate the distribution of questionnaire to the student-respondents.

Likewise, an informed consent letter was also given to the parents and students for ethical consideration. The consent letter contains the purpose of the study and the right to withdraw from participating in the study and the right to confidentiality and how the data will be handled and stored.

Following the completion of the research-made instrument, the researcher tallied and analyzed the data with the assistance of a statistician. The information that was gathered will be structured and then summarized.

For the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, the study employed the following: Utilizing statistical techniques like the weighted mean, the data on the Career Development Domains, Career Readiness, and Career Selection of the students were

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displayed. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to find out if there a relationship existed between Career Development Domains as to Career Selection and Readiness at .05 level of significance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 This study focuses on students' perception in terms of Career Development Domain

Table 1. Perception of student-respondent in terms of Career Development Domain as to Interest

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In terms of interest, the school...		
1. Let's me know what I enjoy and what I do well which makes me evaluate more what career I want to pursue.	3.57	High Level of Awareness
2. Helps me assess the career activities that best fit my significant experiences and passions.	3.49	High Level of Awareness
3. Provides me the motivation and potential for developing my career choice based on the things that I personally and professionally love.	3.44	High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.50	High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderate Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (No Level of Awareness)

Table 1 demonstrates high interest in all Career Development Domain factors. Students learn what they like and are good at, which helps them decide what they want to do. This indicator has the greatest mean indicating that they perceive improvement in the areas of career enjoyment and practicality.

The results also show that in the indicator, *“provides me the motivation and potential for developing my career choice based on the things that I personally and professionally love”*. Though it shows the least mean, it still indicates a high level of awareness.

Overall, the data indicates a high level of awareness, indicating that 10th graders are aware of the interests that can help them choose a career path and be prepared for it.

Table 2. Perception of student-respondent in terms of Career Development Domain as to Skills

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In terms of skills, the school...		
1. considers individualized passion and desire which don't limit me to choose something that doesn't fit my skills.	3.43	High Level of Awareness
2. draws me to be more realistic in choosing a career based on what I can do and develop personally and professionally.	3.53	High Level of Awareness
3. helps me acquire my own inventory of valuable career development foundation skills.	3.50	High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.49	High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderate Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (No Level of Awareness)

The previous table demonstrates a high level of awareness for all indicators of the Career Development Domain regarding skills. In terms of skills, the students make them more realistic when selecting a desired vocation, thereby fostering their personal and professional growth. They may consider the well-compensated positions that are available in the country or the profession.

The results also show that in the indicator *“considers individualized passion and desire which don't limit me to choose something that doesn't fit my skills”* shows the lowest mean but still reflects that Grade 10 has a high level of awareness.

Most 10th graders demonstrate a high awareness of their capabilities. Understanding one's talents can help them enhance their innate abilities, which they may use in their future career. They may use their talents as a significant factor in their job search.

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Table 3. Perception of student-respondent in terms of Career Development Domain as to Problem Solving

[1] Statements	Mean	[2] Verbal Interpretation
[3] In terms of problem solving, the school...		
1. improves and maximizes my decision-making skills in choosing career opportunities.	3.40	High Level of Awareness
2. prepares me in overcoming challenges and organizing my desires that concern my developmental and mental health.	3.49	High Level of Awareness
3. makes me reflect on the moves I should and should not do while in the process of determining the career I want to pursue.	3.49	High Level of Awareness
[4] OVERALL	3.46	High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderate Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (No Level of Awareness)

Table 3 displays a high level of problem-solving awareness across all statements of the Career Development Domain. Regarding problem-solving, the school requires them to consider the steps they must take to determine the career they wish to pursue; it also prepares them to surmount obstacles and organize their desires in terms of their developmental and mental health. It prepares students to be problem-ready and to discover learning opportunities in adversity.

The results also show that in the indicator “improves and maximizes my decision-making skills in choosing career opportunities” has a lowest mean, yet it still interprets as to have a high level of awareness.

Most 10th graders demonstrate a high level of problem-solving awareness. A pupil with problem-solving skills can provide insight into the challenges they may face when choosing a career. They critically consider their options in each circumstance.

Table 4. Perception of student-respondent in terms of Career Development Domain as to Opportunities

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In terms of opportunities, the school...		
1. helps me conceptualize and plan career opportunities that match my individual qualities.	3.42	High Level of Awareness
2. accommodates variety of career opportunities which help me reflect on what fits me best.	3.43	High Level of Awareness
3. leads me in discovering my abilities and capabilities that leads me to think of new career opportunities.	3.47	High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.44	High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderate Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (No Level of Awareness)

Table 4 demonstrates that all indicators of the Career Development Domain demonstrate a high level of opportunity awareness. The school's opportunities lead students to recognize their skills and abilities, which prompts them to consider alternative career paths. The students oversee discovering the career path they wish to pursue.

The results also show that in the statement “helps me conceptualize and plan career opportunities that match my individual qualities”. Though this statement shows the lowest mean, it still indicates a high level of awareness.

All the data indicate a high level of awareness. This indicates that many 10th graders have adequate knowledge in all career-relevant subjects. This also demonstrates that the school's career guidance program has assisted students in strengthening all areas in which they should excel.

3.2 This study focuses on students' Career Readiness

Table 5. Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Self-efficacy

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In planning and choosing my career, I can...		
1. identify the most important components in which I excel and which I need to work on to.	3.50	Very High Level of Awareness
2. acknowledge specific occupations that I could pursue.	3.46	Very High Level of Awareness
3. set goals and identify pathways to the specific career I want.	3.53	Very High Level of Awareness

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4. encourage myself to harness my ability by being committed and determined to my studies for my future goals	3.60	Very High Level of Awareness
5. own a solid idea of what should I do to achieve my goals.	3.59	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.53	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

The students that responded to the survey are classified as having a self-efficacy level that can be seen in the table that is located above. The students had a very high level of awareness in encouraging themselves to harness their potential through commitment and determination to their studies that affects their future goals which earned the highest mean in all the indicators.

Even though the acknowledgement of specific occupations that the students can pursue received the lowest mean score, this nonetheless demonstrates a very high level of awareness.

In general, students in the tenth grade have a healthy awareness of the readiness of their self-efficacy. This demonstrates that their level of self-confidence influences how well they are prepared for the jobs they will have in the future. It increases both their interest in, and dedication to, the career path that they have chosen.

Table 6: Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Teamwork

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In planning and choosing my career, I...		
1. understand that I need to work with others and facilitate team dialogue.	3.47	Very High Level of Awareness
2. seek ways on how to engage myself in collaboration and construction towards team success.	3.50	Very High Level of Awareness
3. assess and evaluate myself as to how I could build relationships towards the group.	3.47	Very High Level of Awareness
4. employ knowledge, abilities, and strengths that complement those of others.	3.54	Very High Level of Awareness
5. exercise managing conflicts effectively and interacting with respect.	3.47	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.49	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

In the table that can be found above, those students who participated in the survey and gave their responses are classified as being prepared for a job. Based on the responses, it is feasible to draw the conclusion that the respondents possess a very high level of awareness regarding all the indicators. The highest means “employ knowledge, abilities, and strengths that complement those of others”.

“Understand that I need to work with others and facilitate team dialogue”, “assess and evaluate myself as to how I could build relationships towards the group”, and “exercise managing conflicts effectively and interacting with respect” these shows that while having the lowest mean score and the same score overall, these indicators imply that the respondents have a very high level of awareness regarding their preparedness for a job.

The findings of this study indicate, in general, that the students who are enrolled in the tenth grade have a very high level of awareness of oneself regarding the preparation level they possess in terms of engaging in a group. This readiness level is measured in terms of the students' ability to work well with others in a group setting. People who are skilled at working together to achieve a common goal create a pleasant experience and atmosphere for those who are immediately surrounding them. This is another indication that they will get along swimmingly with the people that they will be joining up with soon. A strong feeling of collaboration may be an indication that a person is a better person overall and will get along well with their coworkers. This is because people who work well together tend to be more productive.

Table 7. Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Decision Making

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In planning and choosing my career, I...		
1. proactively anticipate my needs and do what should be done first.	3.46	Very High Level of Awareness
2. take control of everything that concerns the career I want to pursue.	3.49	Very High Level of Awareness
3. seek advice from others before taking my plans into action.	3.56	Very High Level of Awareness

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4. relate and apply the concepts I learned in school in deciding for myself.	3.50	Very High Level of Awareness
5. thoroughly assess myself, what's important, what I enjoy, and what I do well.	3.60	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.52	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

One of the markers that students-respondents are prepared for their future careers is decision making, which is presented in the table that is above. Students have a very high level of awareness when it comes to evaluating themselves for what is important to them, what they please themselves, and what they are doing their best.

On the other hand, being proactive in predicting their needs and prioritizing things ranks lowest among all the indicators, even though students still have a very high level of awareness.

In general, by the time students reach the tenth grade, they have demonstrated that they are ready to make decisions regarding the career path that they will pursue. The outcome demonstrates that they have a very high level of awareness regarding the career path that they wish to pursue. Students in the tenth grade may give the impression that they are unsure of what professional route they want to pursue, but they are preparing themselves to make this decision by thinking things over carefully and honestly assessing whether they are a good match for the course or subject that they want to pursue.

Table 8. Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Organization

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
[5] In planning and choosing my career, I...		
1. prioritize things that should be first complied with.	3.53	Very High Level of Awareness
2. pay attention and investigate details the knowledge and information I should know and consider.	3.52	Very High Level of Awareness
3. give focus on tasks completion that observe time management.	3.48	Very High Level of Awareness
4. follow solely my timetable and refrain myself from procrastination.	3.40	Very High Level of Awareness
5. keep myself motivated and resourceful while achieving my goals.	3.55	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.50	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

Table 8 contains the responses of the students who took part in this survey and provides insight into what they envision as their dream employment. The student-respondents have a very high level of awareness, as described in their preparedness in career towards organization, regarding the indicator "keep myself motivated and resourceful while achieving my goals." This indicates that children in grade 10 are directing their thoughts towards their ultimate objective, which may lead to a satisfying choice of profession and overall success in their lives.

On the other hand, students received the lowest mean score for following a timeline and abstaining from procrastinating. Despite this, students nevertheless gained a very high level of awareness on how they will plan and choose their job through organization.

Overall, the students are very aware of how ready they are for a career, as described in the organization. These are the ways that 10th graders try to figure out what they want to do with their lives. They look for things that keep them going on their own. Even though they have work from every class they are taking right now, they can still put a smile on their face and feel confident that they will reach their goals.

Table 9. Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Effective Communication

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In planning and choosing my career, I...		
1. vividly express my thoughts and ideas about what I want to be in the future.	3.51	Very High Level of Awareness
2. put a habit of active listening to let important points sink into me.	3.44	Very High Level of Awareness
3. confidently shares my suggestions and accepts rejections.	3.41	Very High Level of Awareness
4. build positive communication with others.	3.46	Very High Level of Awareness

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5. practice myself when to vent and when to wait to avoid misunderstandings	3.56	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.48	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

Table 9 shows how well the students who replied had prepared themselves for career opportunities in terms of effective communication. The markers of effective communication demonstrated a high level of awareness, with students practicing when they need to release their feelings and when they should avoid misunderstandings with their colleagues. This enables students to be more aware of their surroundings.

Even though they obtained the lowest mean score, they still received a very high level of awareness in terms of how effectively they communicated. This was because they shared their opinions and were open to the rejections of other people.

As part of their career preparation, tenth graders showed a very high level of awareness of effective communication. Despite strain, a high workload, activities, and subjects to master, they were able to stay calm and communicate with people in their area. Clear and effective communication can improve relationships and activities.

Table 10. Readiness of the student-respondents towards career described in Goal-setting

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In planning and choosing my career, I...		
1. plan short-term and long-term goals for my future endeavors.	3.63	Very High Level of Awareness
2. carefully scheme the vision of what to look forward with myself.	3.51	Very High Level of Awareness
3. assure my goals incorporate my interests and values but tied with my desired level of working life.	3.54	Very High Level of Awareness
4. practice reskilling and upskilling to match my goals for my career choice.	3.51	Very High Level of Awareness
5. set goals based on my interests and abilities.	3.66	Very High Level of Awareness
OVERALL	3.57	Very High Level of Awareness

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Very High Level of Awareness), 2.51 – 3.25 (High Level of Awareness), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low Level of Awareness), 1.0 – 1.75 (Very Low Level of Awareness)

It is possible to deduce from the table that is located above that the student respondents are career-ready in terms of goal setting. It is clear from this that, of all the indicators, defining professional objectives that are aligned with their interests and abilities is the most effective strategy for a person to be prepared for a job. It earned a very high level of awareness on how they could be ready in selecting job options after graduating from junior high school.

Students might take into consideration carefully planning a vision of what they must look forward to for themselves, along with practice reskilling and upskilling to match their goals for their career choice, to contain their readiness in terms of career; however, despite having the lowest mean, they still have a very high level of awareness of their readiness in terms of career.

In general, the students' level of preparedness for their future careers demonstrates a very high level of awareness of the aspects stated in goal setting. According to the findings of the researcher, students in the tenth grade are setting goals that will assist them in becoming more knowledgeable about their existing nature skills and capabilities. These goals include expanding their knowledge base, improving their existing nature skills and interests, and reskilling their nature skills and interests so that they are a better fit for the career path that they have chosen. These days, many students are goal oriented. It is plain to observe that they are driven and passionate about the accomplishment of the goals that they have set for themselves. They will be more focused on the things that they desired, and it will allow them to know be clear to their plans and to the placing a timeframe in each. Setting a goal means that they will be more focused on the things that they wanted.

3.3. This study focuses on students' Career Selection

Table 11. Career Selection of student-respondents based on Talents

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In choosing and selecting the appropriate career for me, my talents..		
1. leverage me to show my fullest potential in doing better for the career path I plan to choose.	3.50	Highly manifested

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2. let me align my career preference with my interests.	3.40	Highly manifested
3. leave me a lasting impression of the career option I have.	3.46	Highly manifested
4. fit me in between my defining personal circumstances and evaluating my career choice.	3.44	Highly manifested
5. engage me in the career-planning activities which I enjoy and gives me more determined mind of pursuing the career.	3.54	Highly manifested
OVERALL	3.47	Highly manifested

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Highly manifested), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderately manifested), 1.76 – 2.50 (Somewhat manifested), 1.0 – 1.75 (Not manifested)

Table 11 displays the extent to which talents exhibit themselves in the profession choices made by the student respondents. Based on the data, most respondents highly manifested that participating in career planning activities that they find enjoyable gives them a more determined mind to pursue their career. This gives the students the chance to enjoy the activities because they are aligned to their talents which can they be surer about the career they will select in the future.

On the other hand, the indicator that asked students to "let me align my career preference with my interests" received the lowest mean score but was nevertheless found to be highly manifested in the selection of careers for students based on their talents.

Overall, it is possible to view the process of choosing a profession based on the skills and interests of the students as highly manifested. When planning a future occupation, a student ought to consider their various talents. If a person's talents and career are well matched, it is possible for them to achieve financial success because they will be using their intelligence in activities that they enjoy doing. If they are aware of their strengths and weaknesses, they will be more productive workers.

Table 12. Career Selection of student-respondents based on Abilities

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In choosing and selecting the appropriate career for me, my abilities...		
1. me to plan a career that matches the skills I am good at.	3.56	Highly manifested
2. gives me reflections on whether I am fit or not to the career option designs I have preferred for myself.	3.50	Highly manifested
3. let me compare my potential and self-knowledge to what I want to become.	3.56	Highly manifested
4. draw clearly how the skills I acquired are shaping the goals I have set for future career opportunities.	3.51	Highly manifested
5. help me know myself better leading me to a clearer view of what I want to be.	3.54	Highly manifested
OVERALL	3.53	Highly manifested

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Highly manifested), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderately manifested), 1.76 – 2.50 (Somewhat manifested), 1.0 – 1.75 (Not manifested)

The data collected from the student-respondents on the indicators that describe the profession choice of the students based on their abilities have been compiled into the table that can be found above. It is possible to conclude, given that the respondents show highly manifested with all the indicators and that the means are close to one another, that the students exhibit the selection of their career based on their abilities. Students show that their abilities help them to design their plan career that matches the skills.

Students also use their talents to give self-reflections on whether they are fit to the profession option that they have preferred for themselves. This item obtained the lowest mean but is still viewed as strongly manifested since students utilize their abilities to give self-reflections on whether they are fit to the career choice that they have preferred for themselves.

Grade 10 students' career decision-making skills are strong. Students struggle to choose careers. They should follow their strengths to love their job. The individual can obtain a clearer view of what they want and help set objectives and make efforts to enhance oneself.

Table 13. Career Selection of student-respondents based on Academic Achievement

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
[6] In choosing and selecting the appropriate career for me, my academic achievement...		
1. gives me courage to push through my specific career choice.	3.58	Highly manifested
2. leads me to a clearer vision of the career choice I am planning for myself.	3.49	Highly manifested
3. drags me to a successful career and growth plan for myself.	3.59	Highly manifested
4. guides me to a list of demanding job occupations in the future.	3.49	Highly manifested

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5. draws me clear reflections in comparison of what my performances based on what I really want to pursue.	3.53	Highly manifested
OVERALL	3.53	Highly manifested

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Highly manifested), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderately manifested), 1.76 – 2.50 (Somewhat manifested), 1.0 – 1.75 (Not manifested)

Table 13 shows that there is a clear pattern emerging in the comments given by the respondents regarding the career paths chosen by students based on their academic performance. According to the data shown above, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the respondents exhibit a highly manifested approach concerning academic achievement in selecting their career. Respondents highly demonstrate evidence of how academic achievement draws them to a good profession and occupation in the future.

On the other hand, students still exhibit a highly manifested academic performance that assists them in leading a clearer picture of the career choice that they are planning to themselves and how it guides them to list the difficult jobs and occupations in the future.

In general, the students showed a highly manifested in terms of their choice of career in relation to their academic performance. This demonstrates that the academic performance of the students has a significant impact on the choice of job path that they make. Most students have the goal of achieving high marks so that they can pursue the career of their dreams. Many of them are of the opinion that if they perform well in school, they will be able to go on to have great careers that will benefit both themselves and their families. They are still at an age where they can dream and have high aspirations for the future; for this reason, if they connect their academic performance and job goals, they will be able to obtain a vocation that is the best match for what they can do.

Table 14. Career Selection of student-respondents based on Parents' Advice

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In choosing and selecting the appropriate career for me, my parents...		
1. involve themselves in the decision-making of the career and vocational development I want to pursue.	3.54	Highly manifested
2. encourages me to explore many options available to find the best the fits me.	3.60	Highly manifested
3. recognize their role as facilitator in my career journey.	3.53	Highly manifested
4. keep the discussions and communications open which allows me freely to discuss my thoughts.	3.53	Highly manifested
5. show their support but don't dominate my choices.	3.58	Highly manifested
OVERALL	3.56	Highly manifested

Legend: 3.26 – 4.0 (Highly manifested), 2.51 – 3.25 (Moderately manifested), 1.76 – 2.50 (Somewhat manifested), 1.0 – 1.75 (Not manifested)

Table 14 presents the data that was acquired from the responses of the respondents on the indicators that describe the profession choice of the student-respondents based on the advice given by their parents. It is possible to speculate that the respondents highly manifested with all the indicators, having the means close to each other, and that the students choose appropriate professional paths that they can. Students choose their appropriate career based on how their parents encourage them to explore many options available to find the best career that suits them.

Also, students who keep the discussions and communications open with their parents and allow them to freely discuss their thoughts got the lowest mean yet still interpreted as highly manifested.

Overall, selection of a career based on their parents' advice showed as highly manifested. Students choose their appropriate career based on how their parents encourage them to explore many options available to them. This demonstrates that the respondents continue to have a solid agreement that students continue to have a high regard for the counsel of their parents in terms of selecting a job.

Table 15. Relationship of Career Development Domains to Career Readiness

Career Development Domain	Career Readiness					
	Self Efficacy	Teamwork	Decision Making	Organization	Effective Communication	Goal Setting
Interest	.663**	.573**	.637**	.595**	.644**	.539**

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Skills	.610**	.454**	.486**	.597**	.568**	.425**
Problem Solving	.659**	.433**	.610**	.490**	.615**	.450**
Opportunities	.703**	.581**	.681**	.606**	.619**	.463**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.00001 level (2-tailed)

The association between the career development domains of interest, skills, problem solving, and opportunities as grouped with the students' career readiness as it relates to self-efficacy, teamwork, decision making, organization, effective communication, and goal setting is seen in the table that has been shown above.

According to the findings shown above, the indicators with the highest correlation to self-efficacy include interest, skills, the ability to solve problems, and opportunities. Students who have a strong conviction in themselves are more likely to make effective use of their interests, skills, and problem-solving abilities, as well as the possibilities available to them. This also suggests that they will be able to make decisions that are useful and productive for them, as well as choices that will allow them to be prepared, and that they will have improved their ability to communicate with other individuals.

The least amount of association can be seen between goal setting and interest, abilities, and opportunities, whereas issue solving has the least amount of correlation to teamwork. This suggests that the students will have a tough time being prepared for the process of selecting a career path if they do not become aware of the talents that they already possess and reflect on those talents. This also suggests that it is conceivable for it to indicate that pupils will have a great possibility of being successful in selecting and being prepared for their profession. This is another implication of what this indicates.

With these results, it shows that career development domains indicators have the strongest correlation to self-efficacy. It indicates that pupils who have self-confidence are better able to plan and carry out the necessary actions to handle any potential situations. (Cherry, 2023)

Table 16. Relationship of Career Development Domains to Career Selection

[7]	Career Selection			
[8]	Talents	Abilities	Academic Achievement	Parents' Advice
Career Development Domain				
Interest	.445**	.571**	.494**	.431**
Skills	.500**	.444**	.599**	.578**
Problem Solving	.518**	.404**	.515**	.506**
Opportunities	.555**	.518**	.548**	.532**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.00001 level (2-tailed)

The association between the career development domain which includes interest, skills, problem solving, and opportunities, and the career selection domain which includes talents, abilities, academic achievement, and parents' advice is displayed in the table that can be found above.

According to the findings presented above, the indicators with a high correlation to interest are abilities; the indicator with the highest correlation to skills is academic achievement; and the indicators with the highest correlation to talents are both problem solving and opportunities. This implies that students' interests have a major impact on the occupations they pick but also on their ability to develop existing skills. This is true even if the students do not pursue careers related to their interests.

Overall, this demonstrated that capabilities in all aspects of career development can have a significant impact on a student's capacity to exhibit such talents as part of the process of deciding which professional path to pursue in the foreseeable future. This might also be interpreted to mean that children who have a strong interest in improving their skills in these areas have a larger opportunity to choose a better line of work that considers their natural aptitudes and skills, as well as the preferences and recommendations of their parents, and that these students are more likely to succeed academically.

4. CONCLUSION

The perceptions of the respondents on the Career Development Domain in terms of interest, abilities, the ability to solve problems, and possibilities fell into the category of having a high level of awareness. The respondents had a high level of awareness regarding their readiness for a career in terms of self-efficacy, teamwork, decision making, organization, effective communication, and goal setting. Highly manifested correlations were found between the respondents' career choices and their talents, abilities, academic achievements, and the advice of their parents. There is a significant relationship between Career Development Domains and Career Readiness. There is also a significant relationship between career development domains and career selection. The

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hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between the Career Development Domains to Career Readiness and Career Selection is sustained.

Based on the results and conclusion posted in the study, the following recommendations were formulated: (1) Guidance Counselors may create a program that will engage students to know more about the career path that they may get in the future. (2) Future researchers may regard the importance of the student's readiness in selecting the career path that the students will have. (3) Administration may encourage Guidance counselors, teachers, and students to attend a seminar or workshop that will enhance their ability to choose their career path.

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